

Elementary Education of Muslims in Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract

Education is the pre-eminent device for the socio-economic, political and cultural transformation of any nation or State. At all times society from different social backgrounds has been interested to undergo the avenues of knowledge, transferred and transformed into its people. Several initiatives have been undertaken by the State and Central Government to ensure that the dropout rate of the students studying in schools is as low as possible. The focus of the government has primarily been upon the minorities and marginalized sections of the society which need extra support and care. Several schemes and initiatives have also been undertaken to ensure that child labour is abolished and no child has to work at the cost of his/her education. The government has also undertaken several economic schemes keeping in mind the poor economic condition of the parents who cannot send their children to school or are reluctant in educating them and rather prefer sending them for work. The most popular schemes have been undertaken by the government are Sarva Shiksha Abiyan, Mid-Day Meals, free education for the needy, Digital India Initiative to connect the villages of India with the rest of the world through internet, etc. Several committees have also been formed and reports have been submitted regarding the educational status of Muslims in India such as the Sachar Committee Report, National Commission for Minorities, National Commission for Minority Educational Institutions, etc. but still the condition of Muslim education has not improved as expected and requires special attention. This paper analyses systematically the status of educational development of Muslim children at elementary stage in Andhra Pradesh, which will be leading into making some impressive hallmarks in the annals of education of Muslims in Andhra Pradesh.

Keywords Elementary Education, Muslim children, Enrolment, Andhra Pradesh.

Introduction

Educationally Muslims are very backward in the state. Traditionally, majority of the Muslim population are poor, they are not taking interest in education as there is no such facility available for these folks except the madrasas. Education is considered to be for elites, though the poor are sent to the madrasa to get only religious knowledge/education till recently. In the modern era it is felt that, it is also important to impart education to the marginalized sections of the society.

Roughly, 200 million Muslims live in India. In some parts of the country they are in sufficiently large numbers and in others they are in limited numbers for historical and geographical reasons. In some states the Muslim population exceeds 10 percent. In Andhra Pradesh Muslims constitute 9.16 percent of the total population of the state.

According to the 1991 census, the ratio of Hindu population in Andhra Pradesh was 89.26 percent while it was 91.76 percent according to the 1911 census. The 1971 census showed that there had been continuous decline in the Hindu population, their ratio had come down to 87.72 percent. But during the last decade their population rose upto 89.26 percent.

During the last decade there was a two percent increase in the Muslim population in Andhra Pradesh. In 1911 the Muslim population was 6.65 percent and in 1991 it increased to 8.91 percent.

Geographically, the distribution of Muslim population varies in different areas. For example, in coastal districts like Vishakhapatnam, Vijayanagaram, East and West Godavari, Muslims are meagerly populated. In Nalgonda, Warangal, and Krishna districts their population ranges between five to six percent whereas in the western coastal districts of Guntur and Nellore, Muslim population is around nine percent. After the reorganization of some districts in 1971 the population of Krishna, Nellore and Guntur went up to around nine percent.

Telugu is the dominant language in these districts therefore, Muslims consider it as their mother tongue and medium of instruction which differs from Telangana Muslims and influenced from Hindu Culture. In Rayalseema region's Chittoor district, the southern part of the state (adjacent to Tamil Nadu) the population of Muslims is fairly large. In Kurnool, Cudappa and Anantpur their population is approximately 17, 15 and 17 percent respectively.

According to 2001 census, total Muslim population in United Andhra Pradesh is 69, 86,856 (9.16% of the total population of the state). Of them, 35, 62,239 are males and 34, 24,617 are females. Out of the total Muslim population in the state, 29, 28,569 live in rural areas and 40, 58,287 live in urban areas. Sex ratio works out to 961 females per 1000 males. Literacy rate in the community is 68%. Of them female literacy rate is 59.10%. [1]

In the present Andhra Pradesh, highest Muslim population is found in Kurnool (16.22 per cent) district and the lowest in Srikakulam (0.31 per cent) district. Muslims in the rural areas of the state are basically small and marginal farmers and agricultural labourers and in urban areas most of them are wage labourers, artisans, small traders, etc. According to 2001 census, total Muslim workers are 23,60,983. Of the total workers 1,75,759 are cultivators, 5,15,682 are agriculture labour and 1,44,833 are working in household industry.

After the bifurcation of the Andhra Pradesh the state has become limited to Rayalseema region and Seemandhra region. It has 13 districts i.e. Anantapur, Chittoor, Dr.YSR Kadapa, East Godavari, Guntur, Krishna, Kurnool, Prakasam, Sri Potti Sri Ramulu Nellore, Srikakulam, Visakhapatnam, Vizianagaram, West Godavari.[2] Muslim population in these districts are very less and all together they constitute around 6.5 percent of the total population of the State.

Social and Cultural Aspect

The Andhra Muslims have been little influenced by foreign cultures i.e. Persian and Arab. Barring a few of the Telangana districts, they almost universally speak a variant of Decani i.e. South Decani as their mother tongue and can communicate in Telugu quite well. However, many can manage a smidgen of standard Urdu, largely because of the dominance of Urdu in Islamic publications in India. In their food habits and other secular practices, they are indistinguishable from their Non-Muslim neighbors.

There are mainly two major groups prevailing among the Muslims in the country and the same trend is found in the state i.e. 'Shia' and 'Sunni'. Majority of the Muslims are 'Sunni' where as a large number of population belongs to the 'Shia' sect/community in the state. After the bifurcation of the state large number of 'Shia' Muslim is with the Telangana state. This community mainly concentrated in Hyderabad with is now the part of this (Telangana) state. As mentioned above that except few pockets largely from the urban areas rest of the population in the community is from Sunni sect.

Like women from other communities, Muslim women are differentiated across gender, class, caste and community and are subjected to the interface between gender and community within the Indian social, political and economic context. After more than six decades of independence majority of Muslim women are one of the most disadvantaged, least literate, economically impoverished and politically marginalized sections of Indian society.[3]

Economic Status of the Muslims in the State

Economic wellbeing provides an opportunity to an individual to gain in other field. It empowers an individual or a family with purchasing power, enabling them to acquire subsistence as well as consumption goods to satisfy the basic needs, comfort and leisure. With this freedom an individual or a group can also think of investments, this can take the form of purchase of durable consumption goods and investments in areas like education, health and capital assets. Such investments are critical for increases in future incomes and for sustaining growth at the level of the individual as well as the economy. While economic benefits derived from such an increase in the entitlements are substantial, employment

also has significant non-economic benefits. The belief that one is engaged in some worthwhile activity provides a sense of esteem and well-being to the worker. Ownership of physical assets (especially land) and human capital (especially education) not only affects employment opportunities but also determines occupational patterns.

Relatively poor access to these assets may force workers to remain at the lower end of the labour market hierarchy. Employment, education and investments in physical assets interact dynamically. It has been argued that the positive impact of education crucially depends upon the existence of market (employment) opportunities. Without economic returns to education provided in the form of a higher probability of getting employment or earning higher income, investment in human capital formation will not occur. Similarly, while ownership of physical capital creates opportunities for employment, growth in employment generates resources for new capital formation.

Muslims in Andhra Pradesh are broadly engaged in agriculture as like rest of the population in the state. Many Muslims are also found in various craft work business, some passed on for generations. Significant number are involved in small businesses somewhat known as "Kutir Parishrama." Due to lack of higher education among Muslims in the state their representation among executive level jobs are limited, however many Muslims have held distinguished posts with in state and private sector. In the present state majority of the people are workers. The working population is broadly distributed into four occupation groups. They are, wage labour, petty business, skilled workers such as Tailoring, auto driver, carpentry, electrician, mechanic, agarbathi making, beedi making etc. and employees. Majority of the workers around 73.05% are wage labourers and this category includes both agriculture labour and non-agriculture labour.[4] It is interesting to note that percentage of females found in wage labour among the total workers is more than that of men. Then comes under skilled workers in which most of the people from the Muslim community are engaged in then followed by people who are in petty business. Very less number of the people are employees that too in some districts. In the field of skilled work, the percentage of male is more than female.

- Aim of study**
1. To study the status of literacy rate of Muslims in Andhra Pradesh.
 2. To find out the educational development of Muslim Children at Elementary Stage.
 3. To understand the issues and challenges of Muslim children to attend the school.

Review of Literature

Samir Ghosh (2023) examined the National Education Policy -2020 and suggested that the recommendations will be effective only by development of infrastructure, improving work culture and to some extent it should be modified on the basis of reality.

The main thrust of the welfare of Muslims are focused on the socio-Historical situations of the lower caste Muslims in different life of the Society. According to the Ali and others the conditions of the OBC and Dalits Muslim is even worse in some case of SC Dalits. Ali et al., propound more reservations to the OBC and Dalit Muslims. In this connection, the findings of Sachar and Mishra, reports also have recommended the reservation for the OBC and Dalit Muslims have been endorsed. However, the Muslims Community is unable to make any concrete steps for uplifting the OBC and Dalit Muslims. On the contrary, some groups, particularly, the elites Muslims are demanding the reservation for the whole community on the basis of backwardness after the 65 years of Secular democracy.

Even though it is uncommon among the Muslims to differentiate among them, several studies have done by both colonial anthropologists and the Indian sociologists in post-colonial India, along with several committees, commissions and census reports have also compiled data on the basis of caste and Community. And these reports and census has mentioned and listed several caste groups in Muslim Society (Census India, 1901, 1931). However, the religious, social, political elite of the community completely rejected the caste practices within community till few years ago. Once they accepted its existence, they passed the blame on to the Hindu Social milieu. Before going into intensive discussion about the caste system in Muslims society, let us visit some facts about presence of various caste groups in the lights of reports commission appointed by government.

In this background, first time, at the all India level two such commissions have so far been appointed – Kaka-Kalekar Commission and Mandal Commission. The first backward commission submitted its report in 1955. The Commission emphasized the lower status in caste hierarchy as the determining factor for backward along with other considerations such as educational levels, income levels and representation in public employment. The commission was the first instance in which certain caste and communities among Muslims (and other religious minorities) were also declared backward and brought within the purview of affirmative actions. The second Backward classes commission (Mandal Commission, 1980) too relied on the caste criterion, however, the tangible indicator to ascertain a caste or any social groups 'backward' included lower position in the caste hierarchy, lower age at marriage within the group, higher work participation, higher

Hindu	58.1	0.3	9.2	11.0	12.6	8.4	100.0
Muslim	45.6	0.4	11.2	16.2	16.5	7.8	100.0
Christian	59.2	0.2	12.9	10.9	10.1	6.6	100.0
Others	53.9	0.0	2.8	8.4	15.7	19.2	100.0

Source: DLHS-3, 2007-08

In the above table the data suggested that the educational level of Muslim is better than other religious community. There are around 46 per cent of the sample married women have no education which is very less than the Hindus (58 per cent). Like many other states the percentage of literate without going to school is higher than other religious community. That suggests still large number of children are getting their education either at home or at Madrasa. It is important that the number of children receiving this kind of education in Andhra Pradesh is very less as compared to other states. Table also suggests that the elementary and secondary education among the Muslims is higher than others. While, Muslims are lagging behind at higher secondary stage, just 8 per cent of the children were able to complete 11 or more years of schooling in the state.

Table: 2

Literacy ratio gender wise among major Socio-Religious Communities SRCs - 2021								
Districts	Hindu		Muslim		Christian		Others	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
Srikakulam	67.19	43.62	79.25	61.24	59.75	44.77	80.06	61.53
Vizianagaram	62.2	39.66	77.17	60.14	69.49	51.75	81.38	67.54
Visakhapatnam	69.03	49.26	87	70.97	86.21	73.87	85.90	81.99
E. Godavari	69.64	60.61	82.28	70.31	81.46	71.33	88.29	80.36
W. Godavari	77.81	68.72	83.66	72.58	80.92	73.7	89.05	81.22
Krishna	74.17	63.02	76.28	62.61	75.65	66.48	88.04	76.72
Guntur	71.21	54.06	70.2	48.8	76.01	61.63	83.77	73.80
Prakasam	68.73	44.56	76.84	49.55	78.86	61.96	88.81	76.54
Nellore	72.94	55.9	78.99	58.13	85.45	75.26	93.55	84.75
Cuddapah	75.84	48.75	75.21	52.67	82.94	66	88.30	79.08
Kurnool	65.66	39.08	66.32	42.79	81.3	65.54	82.89	76.58
Anantapur	67.59	42.26	73.87	50.36	88.65	75.49	82.35	82.16
Chittoor	77.48	55.41	78.03	57.4	88.75	78.76	90.24	85.92
Andhra Pradesh	70.73	51.15	77.32	58.27	79.65	66.66	86.36	77.56

Source: Census 2001.

The above table represents literacy rate among the major socio religious group. Highest literacy is found among the male (86 percent) and female (77 percent) in other religion which comprises Jain, Buddhist, and Sikhs. Christian literacy is 73 percent, Male literacy among the Christian is around 79 percent and female literacy is 66 percent. On an average Muslim male (77 percent) is more literate than Muslim female (58.27). The Muslim literacy is more where they constitute less in numbers. These districts are East Godavari, West Godavari, Visakhapatnam, Vizianagram, and Sirkakulam. In districts where the Muslim population are in good numbers such as Kurnool, Guntur, Prakasam etc. in those places female literacy is 42 percent, 48 percent and 49 percent respectively which is less than 50 percent and even less than the state average 63 percent. Similarly, in the Hindu community female are more illiterate than other socio religious group. Their literacy is just 51 percent which is not only less than the state average but also the Muslims. Similarly, the literacy among male in the Hindus (71 percent) is less than other religious community. It is evident from the above analysis that the Muslims are not in a bad condition in many places and they are doing much better than Hindus in the field of education. The above analysis shows that in every religious community women's literacy and education is not given preference especially in the Muslim and Hindu community that too in the rural area.

The literacy rate of the Muslims is much better as compared to other disadvantage group. It should be kept in the mind that majority of the Hindu population in Andhra Pradesh is dominated by the Other Backward Class (OBCs).

Annual Status of Education Report (ASER) in a report found that the attendance of the sampled population shows substantial difference between children from Muslim families and those from the other religious background. In their three visits to the sample schools found that the children from Muslim families were present less in numbers than were children from families with other religious affiliation. In the analysis of data shows that Muslim children are performing better than others but they do not translate into better learning outcome. The data suggest that at the initial stage of schooling i.e. in class I and II, attendance of the Muslim students is good but at the end of the primary stage i.e. class IV and V, attendance of the Muslim students become poor. This reflects the problem of dropout among children is higher as they move upwards in the education ladder.[7]

Graph: 1

In the annual report published in the Andhra Pradesh government website, the condition of the Muslims at elementary level are overall improving as compare to the past. The enrollment level according to the report is above 95 per cent and in some districts such as Kurnool, Anantapur etc. the enrollment level of girls is more than the boys.[8] While the out of school children is higher in Guntur where more than 50 per cent of the school going age children are out of school from the Muslim community girls out of school rate are higher than the boys.

Similarly, the dropout is quit high in the Guntur and Kurnool as compare to other districts of the state at primary stage, it constitutes more than 50 per cent of children who are out of school. At upper primary stage dropout of the children is less but in district which is having highest number of Muslim population have large number of dropouts. Girls leaving out the school more than the boys at this stage in the above mentioned districts.

Table:3

Literacy among Rural and Urban Muslims Literacy in Andhra Pradesh

Muslim Literacy at Rural and Urban Area

S. No	Districts	Rural Literacy			Urban Literacy		
		Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
1	Srikakulam	70.69	49.30	60.21	86.05	70.02	77.89
2	Vizianagaram	66.74	45.92	56.16	83.86	69.39	76.55
3	Visakhapatnam	81.54	58.50	69.98	88.75	75.34	82.31
4	East Godavari	76.58	64.26	70.38	86.13	74.49	80.35
5	West Godavari	81.99	70.52	76.30	85.71	75.02	80.32
6	Krishna	73.75	57.94	65.88	78.78	67.28	73.11
7	Guntur	67.15	42.97	55.13	73.80	55.67	64.78
8	Prakasam	75.74	46.11	61.11	79.47	57.74	68.66
9	Nellore	79.15	55.69	67.41	78.76	61.58	70.25
10	Cuddapah	73.89	48.63	61.40	76.77	57.48	67.25
11	Kurnool	65.91	37.73	52.07	66.92	50.23	58.76
12	Anantapur	71.21	44.06	57.86	75.68	54.67	65.37
13	Chittoor	76.20	53.89	65.14	82.27	65.65	74.12
Andhra Pradesh		73.89	51.96	63.00	80.23	64.20	72.29

Source: Census 2001

The above table reflects the literacy status among the Muslims at rural and urban place. We can see that the rural literacy in the state is 63 percent among the Muslims in which male are 74 percent literate and females are only 52 percent literate. Female literacy in the rural area is worse as compare to the state average.

Graph: 2

In the Urban area the literacy among the Muslims were 72 percent. Only 64 percent of female are literate as compare to males 80 percent. Though, the urban females are more literate that the rural female, but their condition is almost similar. Both at rural and urban place Muslim males are doing well but in districts like Kurnool, Chittoor, Kadappa etc. where the Muslim population is in large number there the condition of female literacy is worse. In these district women literacy is below 50 percent in rural area and just 57 percent in the Urban vicinity. It is the fact that women have been denied modern education in both rural and urban area in most of the district for whatever reasons.

Enrollment and Dropout

The enrollment and dropout cases among the Muslims gain much attention after the Sachar Committee Report tabled in 2006. It is this committee that brought or highlights the condition of the Muslim in the field of education. It is not that there was no study on Muslim education at all. Some individuals had worked on the educational level of the Muslim at elementary stage but that too at a very micro level and that study is very limited. Those studies were not focusing the condition of the community in the field of Modern education. The attentions towards Muslim education especially primary education have not gain much importance in the academia as well as other institution.

In Andhra Pradesh no such study was taken so far at a neither big level nor do we come across any micro study about the educational condition of the Muslim in the state. District Information System on Education (DISE) did start collecting data on Muslims from 2006-07 onwards. With the help of those data we tried to access the education level of total enrolled Muslim children at the elementary stage.

Table: 4

Enrollment at a Glance

Enrollment Status at Elementary Stage in (%)					
Year	General	Schedule Caste	Schedule Tribe	OBC	Muslims

2006-07	23.63	17.41	8.9	41.21	8.84
2007-08	23.45	17.16	8.75	41.41	9.21
2008-09	23.8	16.82	8.72	41.12	9.54
2009-10	23.65	17.12	9.08	42.8	8.06

Source: District Information System for Education (DISE)

As we know that in most of the southern parts of India majority of the population belongs to the other backward class (OBC) section of the society which has its impact on enrollment as well. The above table represents the total enrollment of Andhra Pradesh.

Graph:3

Enrollment of children of different socio-religious group in AP during 2006-07 to 2009-10

In proportion to the population the enrollment of Muslims is much better than many other states. In the year 2006-07 the Muslim enrollment is more than 8 per cent, whereas the enrollment of Schedule Caste is 17 per cent, Scheduled Tribe is 9 per cent and OBC is 41 per cent. In the next academic year 2007-2008, there was a slight decline in the enrollment of SC (0.25 per cent), ST (0.15 per cent) and General (0.18 per cent) student where as an increase in OBC (0.20 per cent) and Muslims (0.37 per cent) enrollment. The enrollment of Muslim student has increased by 0.33 per cent in the year 2008-09. But there is a sharp decline in the enrollment in the year 2009-2010 by 1.48 per cent, whereas, the enrollment of other disadvantage groups i.e. SC, ST and OBC, enrollment have improved by 0.30 per cent, 0.36 per cent and 1.68 per cent respectively at the elementary level.

Table: 5

District-wise Enrollment of Students in 2012-13

Districts	GEN	SC	ST	OBC	MUSLIM
Anantapur	107075	15436	24991	288744	50495
Chittoor	136462	18641	27429	230431	52821
Kadapa	155776	12362	14357	146858	67380
East Godavari	194579	23061	34611	274771	8039

Guntur	186528	22710	44745	192073	58505
Kurnool	144632	19088	17107	300965	96335
Nellore	77307	15350	43286	135507	32380
Srikakulam	31181	5762	25443	254413	941
Visakhapatnam	142695	7351	117109	236552	5251
Vizianagaram	23195	5544	39155	196971	332
Warangal	51599	17676	100128	236515	22147
West Godavari	125394	19752	17022	203942	7721

Source: DISE Data

The above table shows the total enrollment of students' category wise in the present state excluding Telangana. This data suggests that Muslims in districts such as Kurnool, Kadapa, Guntur, Chittoor etc. are more inclined towards modern education, but still a large number of students are not being able to get the benefits of free education. Its' also seen that a good number of student are taking admission in class I, but subsequently their enrollment drops till class V. More than thirty percent students left school till they reach class VIII.

Table: 6

District-wise Enrollment of Muslim children during 2006-2012						
Districts	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12
Anantapur	9.33	9.81	9.94	9.51	9.24	8.98
Chittoor	9.58	9.79	9.95	9.66	9.33	9.6
Cuddapah	14.4	14.88	14.56	14.12	13.19	14.48
East Godavari	1.36	1.29	1.34	1.27	1.16	1.23
Guntur	8.92	8.8	9.46	8.77	9.44	9.7
Krishna	5.87	5.81	5.97	5.58	5.26	5.58
Kurnool	14.23	14.37	14.48	13.55	13.7	13.49
Nellore	7.5	7.67	7.99	7.58	8.18	8.63
Prakasam	5.85	5.98	6.73	6.08	6.12	6.26
Srikakulam	0.22	0.24	0.26	0.22	0.25	0.22
Visakhapatnam	1.22	1.28	1.44	1.07	1.09	1.04
Vizianagaram	0.44	0.38	0.41	0.4	0.38	0.32
West Godavari	1.42	1.86	1.76	1.56	1.59	1.57
Andhra Pradesh	6.18	6.32	6.48	6.11	6.07	6.24

Source: DISE Data

Graph:4

Enrolment of Muslim Children in Andhra Pradesh

The above table shows the enrollment of the Muslim over a span of 6 years. Annually on an average around 6 percent of the Muslims are getting enrolled at primary level. There is a marginal improvement in the enrollment rate, in the year 2008-09 the state got maximum enrollment i.e. 6.48 percent but after this year the enrollment declines around 0.37 percent further it declines .04 percent in the year 2010-11. In the year 2011-2012 the enrollment slightly increases by 0.17 percent. Kadapa is having the maximum 14.27 percent of Muslim children in the last six years followed by Guntur 14 percent, Chittoor 9.7 percent, Anantapur 9.5 percent and Guntur 9.2 percent.

Conclusion

After the bifurcation of the Andhra Pradesh majority of the Muslim population are in the state of Telangana. In the present Andhra Pradesh Muslims are concentrated mainly in the district of Kurnool, Guntur, Kadapa, Anantapur etc. in other district Muslims are in very small numbers. In above mentioned district the level of education among the Muslim is very poor. Literacy rate is below 50 percent as compared to other socio-religious community. Moreover, women's education in these districts are far less than other community women. According to the Sachar Committee Report these low levels of literacy and education among the Muslim women is due to lack of availability of schools in the locality, language, safe environment etc. The above data suggests that more boys are leaving schools in subsequent classes than the girls. This trend is not completely in favour that lack of school, language, and infrastructure, but there are other factors that are actively affecting the children's education initially at primary subsequently at higher level of education.

In spite of the drawback or deficiency in many areas especially in the field of education Muslims are doing much better than other states such as Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan etc. Not only in the field of education but also in economic activities Muslims are very poor and majority of the population are daily wage labourers. They earn their livelihood through labour and petty business.

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